

LIST OF THE CMIP5-DRIVEN HISTORICAL AND SCENARIO RUNS OF THE MED-CORDEX BASELINE RUNS

version 0: S. Somot, January 2020

version 1: S. Somot, March 2021

version 2: S. Somot, January 2022, merging Phase 1 and Phase 2 run lists

Version 3: S. Somot, I. Parras-Berrocal, 20 April 2026, update the model names to match with the literature and official IPCC Interactive Atlas naming

In Med-CORDEX, 19 scenario runs have been performed with 11 different RCSM configurations and by 8 different institutes. 6 different CMIP5 GCMs and 3 different RCP scenarios are covered. This includes phase 1 and phase 2 runs.

Simulations done, Simulations in preparation

Model naming, model_id	Driving GCM	Scenario	Period	Simulations used in the IPCC-AR6 Interactive Atlas	Status	Last update
CNRM-RCSM4	CNRM-CM5, r1i1p1	RCP26	1951-2100		done	2022-01-20
CNRM-RCSM4	CNRM-CM5, r1i1p1	RCP45	1951-2100	Yes	done	2022-01-20
CNRM-RCSM4	CNRM-CM5, r1i1p1	RCP85	1951-2100	Yes	done	2022-01-20
ENEA-PROTHEUSv2	CNRM-CM5, r1i1p1	RCP45	1979-2100		done	
CLMcom-GUF-CCLM5-0-9-NEMOMED12-3-6	EC-Earth, r12i1p1	RCP85	1950-2099	Yes	done	2019-11-24
LMD-LMDZ4-NEMOMED8v1	IPSL-CM5A-MR, r1i1p1	RCP85	1950-2100	Yes	done	
LMD-LMDZ4-NEMOMED8v1	IPSL-CM5A-MR, r1i1p1	RCP45	1950-2100	Yes	done	
LMD-LMDZ4-NEMOMED8v2	IPSL-CM5A-MR, r1i1p1	RCP85	1950-2100	Yes	done	

LMD-LMDZ4-NEMOMED8v2	CNRM-CM5, r1i1p1	RCP85	1950-2100	Yes	done	
LMD-LMDZ4-NEMOMED8v2	MPI-ESM-MR, r1i1p1	RCP85	1950-2100	Yes	done	
IPSL-MORCEMED	IPSL-CM5A-MR, r1i1p1	RCP85	1989-2035		done	
CMCC-CCLM4-21-NEMOMFSv1 (50km)	CMCC-CM, r1i1p1	RCP85	1950-2099	Yes	done	
CMCC-CCLM4-21-NEMOMFSv1 (50km)	CMCC-CM, r1i1p1	RCP45	1950-2099	Yes	done	
CMCC-CCLM4-21-NEMOMFSv2 (12km)	CMCC-CM, r1i1p1	RCP85	1960-2100		done	2019-11-15
CMCC-CCLM4-21-NEMOMFSv2 (12km)	CMCC-CM, r1i1p1	RCP45	1960-2100		done	2019-11-15
UBEL-EBUPOM2c	MPI-ESM-LR, r1i1p1	RCP85	1950-2100	Yes	done	2020-11
AWI-GERICS-ROM44	MPI-ESM-LR, r1i1p1	RCP85	1950-2099	Yes	done	
AWI-GERICS-ROM22	MPI-ESM-LR, r1i1p1	RCP85	1950-2099	Yes	done	2020-11
AWI-GERICS-ROM22	MPI-ESM-LR, r1i1p1	RCP45	1950-2099	Yes	done	2020-11